

A.C. Polarographic Studies on the Nature of the Capacity Peaks Observed with Organic Compounds at the Dropping Mercury Electrode. Part II. Effect of the Change of the Indifferent Electrolyte

S. L. Gupta and S. K. Sharma

The effect of the change in the supporting electrolyte (from KCl to KI) on the nature of the capacity peaks has been studied with such organic compounds as are known to provide either tensammetric or reduction peaks. The effect of change of indifferent electrolyte on the magnitude of these peaks and on their peak potentials is similar and their nature cannot be distinguished by this test. The reasons for this phenomenon have been discussed. Non-appearance of any change in the depression of the capacity of the double layer, caused by such substances exhibiting tensammetric peaks, and the tremendous change in the case of substances providing reduction peaks, when the supporting electrolyte is changed from KCl to KI, may be utilized in the determination of the nature of the capacity peaks observed with organic compounds at the d.m.e. in pulsating field.

The effect of organic compounds on the dropping mercury electrode (d. m. e.) capacity in pulsating field is responsible for the peaks observed. The peaks may be broadly classified into those caused by (a) desorption and (b) chemical reaction (reduction or oxidation). According to Hacopian¹ these two classes of peaks can be distinguished by the fact that the peak potential of the chemical peaks does not vary with the concentration of the surface-active solutes, whereas the peak potential varies linearly with the logarithm of the concentration in the case of desorption peaks. The general theory, proposed by Doss and Gupta², indicates, however, that the desorption peaks can also occur at a fixed potential, irrespective of the concentration of the solute. Gupta and Agarwal³ offered a tentative classification of these peaks, following the effect of change of the indifferent electrolyte on the magnitude and position of such peaks.

The present investigation deals with further detailed and systematic studies on the nature of the capacity peaks, observed with several organic compounds, providing either tensammetric peaks or reduction peaks, by changing the indifferent electrolyte from KCl to KI.

EXPERIMENTAL

Nitrophenols (*o*- and *p*-) (B.D.H.) and *p*-nitrobenzoic acid (M & B) were recrystallised before use, whereas *m*-nitrophenol was Merck's pure chemical. Nitrobenzene (B. D. H., A. R.), *o*-cresol (E. P., B.D.H.), pyridine, and *n*-amyl alcohol (Baker analysed reagent grade), isopropanol (E. Merck), and benzaldehyde (B.D.H.) were redistilled in an all-glass fractionating column and the middle one-thirds of the distillates were used for the experiments. Cerfak was a commercial detergent and bromothymol blue used was of B. D. H. indicator quality. Mercury used for dropping electrode was further purified by passing through Meyer's column, washed several times with distilled water, dried, passed through a sintered glass filter, and finally distilled under vacuum. All other chemicals used were of A.R. (B.D.H.) quality. The d. c. potentials were applied with respect to the S.C.E. and all the experiments were carried out at a constant temperature of $30^{\circ} \pm 0.5^{\circ}$ and a *pH* of 10.8.

1. *Austr. J. Chem.*, 1953, 6, 211.
2. *Science & Culture*, 1950, 22, 102.
3. *Kolloid Z.*, 1958, 163, 130.
4. *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1952, 36A, 493.

Procedure.—The apparatus employed in the present investigation was the same as described by Doss and Gupta⁴ with the only modification that the series resistance was made as small as possible. This consisted in applying to the d.m.e. 50 c/s a.c. ripple of ± 40 mv (r. m. s) over the d. c. potential and observing the alternating component of the resulting pulsating current. As the capacitive impedance of the d.m.e. was much higher than the rest of the impedance of the system, the magnitude of the alternating current afforded a measure of the d.m.e. capacity.

Potassium chloride, potassium perchlorate, potassium thiocyanate, and potassium iodide (each 0.1 molar) were used as indifferent electrolytes. The results have been expressed in terms of the % increase (with sign) of the a. c., providing practically the % increase in the average differential capacity. The d.m.e. was cathodic throughout the measurements and its constants were: $m=4.564$ mg./sec. and $t=1.8$ sec. per drop in 0.1M-KCl, open circuit. The results are shown graphically in Fig. 1 and 2.

DISCUSSION

Fig. 1 shows a small decrease in the magnitude of the peak in the depression of the capacity of the double layer when KCl is changed to KI. The decrease is in the order: KI > KCNS > KCl > KClO₄. The peak potential is practically constant and is independent of the nature of the supporting electrolyte.

FIG. 1. Effect of tensammetric peak (0.004% bromothymol blue) in various supporting electrolytes. Curves 1-4 refer respectively to KClO₄, KCl, KCNS, and KI (0.1M each).

From Fig. 2 it appears that although the extent of adsorption in 0.1*M*-KCl is small, the magnitude of the peak is quite large. The decrease in the magnitude of the peak as well as in the depression of the capacity of the double layer is quite large when the supporting electrolyte is changed from KCl to KI. The change is again in the same order as in the above case. The peak potential is also practically independent of the nature of the electrolyte.

FIG. 2. Effect of reduction peak ($4 \times 10^{-4}M$ nitrobenzene) in various supporting electrolytes. Curves 1-4 refer to the same electrolytes in order as in Fig 1.

From Table I it appears that with organic substances with tamsammetric peaks, there is only a small decrease in the magnitude of the peak when the electrolyte is changed from KCl to KI, whereas with those providing reduction peaks, the magnitude of the peak is decreased to a very large extent when the indifferent electrolyte is changed, except with *p*-nitrophenol and benzaldehyde, peak potentials of which are -1.0 and -1.46 volts respectively.

Table I shows that the substances providing tamsammetric peaks produce very little change in the depression of the double layer capacity when the electrolyte is changed from KCl to KI, whereas with those producing reduction peaks, there is a very large diminution

in the depression of the capacity when KCl is changed for KI. Incidentally, the values of the double layer capacity corresponding to the maximum depression in the capacity have been recorded in both the electrolytes used.

TABLE I

$pH = 10.8$. 50 c/s. ± 40 mv (r.m.s.). Temp. = $30^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$.

Substances.	Supporting electrolyte = 0.1M-KCl.			Supporting electrolyte=0.1M-KI.		
	Peak magnitude.	Peak potential.	%Diminution of capacity.	Peak magnitude.	Peak potential.	%Diminution of capacity.
Tensammetric peaks.						
0.004% Bromothymol blue	108%	-0.06v	51.0%	70.%	-1.96v	50.0
1% <i>o</i> -Cresol	106	-1.24	60.7	188	-1.25	60.0
1% Pyridine	202	-1.42	60.2	270	-1.40	63.0
1% <i>n</i> -Amyl alcohol	217	-1.25	84.7	175	-1.23	82.8
0.08 % Corfak	128	-1.28	91.0	136	-1.28	93.0
5% Isopropanol						
I Peak	20	-0.17		No peak	..	57.0
II Peak	46	-1.20	59.0	39	-1.19	
Reduction peaks.						
$2 \times 10^{-4}M$ Nitrobenzene	120	-0.66	23.3	14	-0.68	2.7
$4 \times 10^{-4}M$ <i>o</i> -Nitrophenol	77	-0.83	22.9	38	-0.85	2.2
$4 \times 10^{-4}M$ <i>m</i> -Nitrophenol	159	-0.82	18.7	38	-0.82	1.3
$4 \times 10^{-4}M$ <i>p</i> -Nitrophenol	202	-1.00	35.0	155	-0.98	1.7
$4 \times 10^{-4}M$ <i>p</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	143	-0.67	27.0	35	-0.66	3.0
$4 \times 10^{-4}M$ Benzaldehyde	293	-1.46	44.0	291	-1.45	30.0

In general, the effect of change of the electrolyte from KCl to KI on the % a.c. versus d.c. potential curves of all the organic substances studied in the present investigation can be divided in two parts. The first part deals with the effect of the change of the electrolyte on the magnitude of the peak and position of the peak potential at higher cathodic potentials, whereas the second part relates to the depression of the capacity of the double layer at lower cathodic potentials caused by these organic substances. Fig. 1 and 2 show that the peak potential remains practically constant and is independent of the nature of the electrolyte, indicating no reaction between the organic substance and the supporting electrolyte. This fact is further confirmed by the a.c. polarographic studies of Cd^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ions in KCl and KI as supporting electrolytes. Here the peak potential of Cd^{2+} is shifted to more cathodic values, viz., (from -0.63 v to -0.81 v w.r.t. satd. calomel electrode) when the electrolyte is changed from KCl to KI, whereas the peak potential of Zn^{2+} remains practically constant in both the electrolytes used. The change in peak potential of Cd^{2+} is due to complex formation between Cd^{2+} and I^- , whereas no such complex is formed between Zn^{2+} and I^- . It can also be seen from the above figures that there is a small diminution in the magnitude of the bromothymol blue peak, which is known to provide tensammetric peak with the change of the indifferent electrolyte from $KClO_4$ to KI, whereas there is a tremendous change in the magnitude of the peak due to nitrobenzene, which shows reduction peak under similar conditions. The order of diminution of the peaks is: $KI > KCNS > KCl > KClO_4$, which can be explained on the basis of their surface-active nature of the anions of

the electrolytes and their specific hindrance on the electrode processes. It was therefore thought at one time that the effect of change of the electrolyte from KCl to KI might elucidate the nature of the capacity peaks observed with organic compounds. This finds support from the further data recorded in Table I, except for *p*-nitrophenol, benzaldehyde, and the first peak of isopropanol, which show deviation from the above conclusion. Later on, it has been found that all those organic substances, which are known to provide reduction peaks but have peak potentials as—1.0 volt or greater than this, behave very similarly to tensammetric peaks on this test. It is therefore concluded that it is not possible to determine the nature of the peaks observed with organic compounds by this test. The behaviour of the iodide film on the mercury surface seems to be almost similar on both the types of the peaks. The magnitudes of the peak of those organic compounds, peak potential of which is about—0.8 volt or less, are affected to a very large extent because of the hindrance of the electrode process by the adsorbed iodide film, whereas the magnitude of peaks of such organic substances, peak potentials of which are more than—0.8 volt, are less affected because of the desorption of the iodide film from the electrode surface. The fact that the magnitude of the peak becomes less and less affected as the peak potential becomes more and more cathodic, suggests that the desorption of the iodide film from the surface is not sharp. From Table I it appears that although *p*-nitrophenol and benzaldehyde are known to produce reduction peaks⁵, these behave very similar to tensammetric peaks, whereas the first peak of isopropanol, which is tensammetric, behaves very similar to reduction peak on changing the electrolyte from KCl to KI. Some of the conclusions of Gupta and Agarwal³, which now seem to be faulty, can also be explained on the basis of the above conclusions. It can therefore be concluded that it is not possible to determine the nature of the peaks observed with organic compounds by studying the effect of the change of the supporting electrolytes on the magnitude and position of the peak potential.

Table I also shows that there is a great change in the depression of the capacity caused by the organic substances producing reduction peaks, whereas there is practically no change in the depression of the capacity caused by such organic substances, exhibiting tensammetric peaks, by changing the supporting electrolyte from KCl to KI. The % depression of the double layer capacity, caused by substances showing reduction peaks, becomes very small if KI is used in place of KCl as the indifferent electrolyte. It may be pointed out that the change in the double layer capacity in the case of benzaldehyde is not so great as in other cases of reduction peaks, which may be due to the fact that its peak potential is negative, i.e.,—1.46 volts or it produces only tensammetric peak at alkaline pH; this needs further investigation. The fact that there is practically no change in the capacity of the electrical double layer caused by substances producing tensammetric peaks and that there is great change in the case of substances exhibiting reduction peaks, when KCl is changed for KI can be used for the determination of the nature of the capacity peaks observed with organic compounds at the dropping mercury electrode in pulsating field.

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
BIBLA COLLEGE,
PLANI, RAJASTHAN.

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